

HAEMATOLOGICAL PROFILE ALTERATIONS IN OCCUPATIONALLY EXPOSED POPULATIONS OF QUETTA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Occupational exposure to urban air pollution has been consistently linked with adverse health outcomes. Chronically exposed population to vehicular emissions are at risk of hematological alterations, yet little evidence exists for local populations. **Objective:** To assess alterations of haematological indices as result of chronic occupational exposure to vehicular emissions. To provide guide-line to occupational health policies for protective interventions. **Methods:** A cross-sectional comparative study was conducted recruiting 90 participants including, Exposed group (traffic police, bus drivers, hawkers) and Unexposed group (teachers, clerks, students). Blood samples were analyzed for platelet indices (PLT, PDW, PDWC, PLCC, PLCR, MPV), coagulation parameters (PT, APTT), white and red blood cell counts. Descriptive statistics (Mean \pm SD, range) were used for group comparisons. **Results:** Platelet counts were significantly lower in exposed groups with mean value of $(223.2 \pm 28.05 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L})$ compared to unexposed $(271 \pm 15.9 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L})$. Mean platelet volume (MPV) was comparable, though slightly reduced in exposed workers. Coagulation analysis showed prolonged PT in exposed $(13.55 \pm 0.64 \text{ sec})$ compared to unexposed group $(12.16 \pm 0.57 \text{ sec})$. APTT was found shortened in exposed $(26.59 \pm 0.58 \text{ sec})$ than unexposed group $(29.93 \pm 1.19 \text{ sec})$. White blood cell counts were consistently higher in exposed groups, indicating systemic inflammatory activation. Demographic data revealed longer exposure duration and higher smoking prevalence in traffic police, drivers and hawkers. **Conclusion:** Individuals occupationally exposed to vehicular emissions is associated with altered platelet indices, coagulation imbalance along with changes in hematological parameters. These findings highlight potential risks for thrombosis and cardiovascular disorders. Preventive strategies such as protective gear, reduced exposure duration and health monitoring are recommended.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the leading environmental risk factors contributing to global morbidity and

mortality. Evidences linking chronic exposure to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (1,2).

Vehicular emissions is the major source of air pollution, contributing to ambient particulate matter (PM), nitrogen oxides, carbon monoxide and volatile organic compounds. These pollutants have been shown to trigger oxidative stress, systemic inflammation and endothelial dysfunction, which in turn may influence haematological and coagulation parameters (3, 4).

Occupationally exposed group such as traffic police, bus drivers and street hawkers are chronically exposed to vehicular emissions. Studies conducted in developing regions of the world have demonstrated alterations in platelet indices, leukocyte counts and coagulation profiles in individuals occupationally exposed to urban air pollutants (5,6). These haematological changes are not only indicative of systemic inflammation but also serve as early biomarkers of cardiovascular and thrombotic risks (7,8)

Balochistan is the largest province of Pakistan, remains understudied in terms of occupational health and air pollution related risks. Provincial capital, Quetta is a rapidly urbanizing with growing traffic congestion, poor emission control and limited monitoring of air quality indices. The lack of region-specific epidemiological data is hampering the development of targeted

interventions, health policies and occupational safety regulations.

This study is designed to investigate haematological and coagulation alterations in occupationally exposed group (traffic policemen, bus drivers, hawkers) compared with unexposed control group (teachers, clerks, students). The findings aim to provide baseline evidence for occupational health risk assessment and contribute to public health interventions in urban Balochistan.

Methodology

Demographic information, occupational history, duration of exposure and smoking status were collected from study cohort, using structured questionnaires (Table 1). Venous blood samples were drawn under aseptic conditions and haematological parameters such as red blood cell (RBC) count, white blood cell (WBC) count and platelet indices were analyzed using an automated haematology analyzer. Coagulation parameters, including prothrombin time (PT) and activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) were measured with a standard coagulometer. Descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, mean \pm SD) were computed for each group and comparisons were made between exposed and unexposed participants as well as within subgroups.

Results

Haematological analysis revealed that mean platelet count (PLT) was lower in the exposed group ($223.2 \pm 28.05 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) when compared to the unexposed group ($271 \pm 15.9 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$). Other platelet indices, including platelet distribution width (PDW-S, PDW-C), platelet large cell count

(PLCC), platelet large cell ratio (PLCR) and mean platelet volume (MPV) showed minimal differences across the cohort (Table 1). The exposed group reported longer occupational exposure (5–12 years) compared the unexposed group (1–3 years). Smoking prevalence was notably higher among bus drivers and hawkers.

Table 1. Demographic and Occupational Characteristics with Subgroup Haematological Parameters

Group	Age (years)	Exposure (years)	Smokers	Non-smokers	PLT ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) Mean \pm SD	PDWS Mean \pm SD	MPV Mean \pm SD
Traffic police	28–40	5–12	10	5	222 \pm 21.3	13.1 \pm 1.74	11.2 \pm 0.87
Bus drivers	25–40	7–12	13	2	228 \pm 33.4	13.3 \pm 1.68	11.1 \pm 0.96
Hawkers	22–35	5–10	11	4	218 \pm 29.1	12.8 \pm 1.96	10.8 \pm 0.93
Teachers	25–45	1–2	5	10	267 \pm 15.0	14.3 \pm 3.81	11.6 \pm 1.47
Clerks	30–45	1–3	7	8	263 \pm 15.3	12.9 \pm 2.69	11.1 \pm 1.20
Students	20–30	1–2	3	12	283 \pm 9.35	13.1 \pm 1.44	11.3 \pm 0.89

Coagulation parameters demonstrated marked alterations. The exposed group exhibited prolonged prothrombin time (PT: 13.55 ± 0.64 sec) in comparison to the unexposed group (12.16 ± 0.57 sec), while activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) was shortened to 26.59 ± 0.58 sec vs. 29.93 ± 1.19 sec (Table 2).

Table 2. Platelet Indices and Coagulation Profile of Exposed and Unexposed Groups

Parameter	Exposed (n=45) Mean \pm SD	Unexposed (n=45) Mean \pm SD
PLT ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	223.2 \pm 28.05	271 \pm 15.9
PDWS	13.11 \pm 1.77	13.47 \pm 2.82
PDWC	34.32 \pm 1.71	34.52 \pm 2.12
PLCC	74.44 \pm 26.6	84.20 \pm 33.89
PLCR	32.86 \pm 6.33	33.99 \pm 7.79
MPV	11.09 \pm 0.92	11.38 \pm 1.20
PT (sec)	13.55 \pm 0.64	12.16 \pm 0.57
APTT (sec)	26.59 \pm 0.58	29.93 \pm 1.19

Discussion

This cross-sectional comparative study was conducted in Quetta city from January to June 2023. The study cohort involved 90 male participants, aged between 20–45 years. Participants were divided into two groups, exposed (n = 45; traffic policemen, bus drivers,

and hawkers) and unexposed group (n = 45; teachers, clerks, and students). This study highlights the occupational exposure to vehicular emissions and roadside pollutants is associated with measurable alterations in haematological and coagulation parameters. Exposed group (traffic policemen, bus drivers, hawkers) showed lower platelet counts and altered coagulation times compared to unexposed controls (teachers, clerks,

students), suggesting early haematological stress from chronic environmental exposure. Reduced platelet counts in the exposed group are consistent with previous findings linking air pollution to bone marrow suppression and increased platelet turnover (9).

Although other platelet indices showed minimal differences, subtle shifts may still reflect changes in platelet activation, similar to trends reported among traffic police in Karachi (10). The prolonged PT and shortened APTT in exposed individuals point to haemostatic imbalance, with potential for both bleeding and thrombotic risks. These results align with evidence that air pollution induces systemic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and prothrombotic states (3,4,11). Overall, the findings highlight occupational exposure is a public health concern. Regular medical surveillance, use of protective measures and stricter vehicular emission regulations are needed to reduce long-term cardiovascular risks in highly exposed group.

Conclusion

Chronic occupational exposure to vehicular emissions and roadside pollutants was associated with reduced platelet counts and altered coagulation profiles among exposed workers in Quetta. These subclinical changes may induce

long-term cardiovascular risk, underscoring the need for preventive strategies such as health monitoring, protective measures and strict emission controls strategies.

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